

Use of Advertising Appeal in Magazine Advertisements: Atlas Magazine Example

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ABSTRACT

With the development of global competition, the need for brands to differentiate from each other has emerged. This differentiation is reflected not only in the quality of the product or service offered, but also in the advertising messages that introduce these products and services to target audiences. One of the most effective methods of differentiating advertising messages is the use of advertising appeals. Brands use two types of advertising appeals, rational and emotional, to differentiate their advertising messages. The type of advertising appeal to be used varies depending on various variables such as the brand's goals and the characteristics of the audience it wants to reach. This study aims to analyze how advertising appeals are used in magazine advertisements as an advertising medium that maintains its effectiveness in the context of sectoral diversity. In this direction, 78 advertisements in Atlas magazine between January 2021 and May 2021 were examined using purposive sampling and content analysis, one of the qualitative research methods. As a result of the analysis, percentages were calculated and the most used appeals and almost never used appeals were determined. The most commonly used emotional appeal in magazine ads is the quality appeal. They frequently incorporate the quality element into their ads to meet customer demands and expectations. It has been analyzed that the emotional appeals of guilt, scarcity, music, and individuality are relatively less prevalent. This also suggests that brands avoid using guilt and scarcity appeals to avoid creating negative impressions in the minds of magazine buyers.

Keyword: Advertising, Magazine Advertising, Advertising Appeals, Emotional Appeal.

Dergi Reklamlarında Çekicilik Kullanımı: Atlas Dergisi Örneği

ÖZET

Küresel rekabetin gelişmesiyle birlikte, markaların birbirinden farklılaşması ihtiyacı doğmuştur. İfade edilen bu farklılaşma, sunulan ürün ya da hizmetin niteliğinin yanında, bu ürün ve hizmetlerin hedef kitlelere tanıtılmasını sağlayan reklam mesajlarında da kendisini göstermektedir. Reklam mesajlarında farklılaşmanın en etkili yöntemlerinden birisi, reklam çekiciliklerinin kullanılmasıdır. Markalar, reklam mesajlarında farklılaşmak için rasyonel ve duygusal olmak üzere iki tür reklam çekiciliğinden yararlanmaktadır. Hangi reklam çekiciliğinin kullanılacağı, markanın hedefleri, ulaşmak istediği kitlenin özellikleri gibi çeşitli değişkenlere göre farklılık göstermektedir. Bu çalışma, etkinliğini koruyan bir reklam mecrası olarak dergi reklamlarında sektörel çeşitlilikler bağlamında reklam çekiciliklerinin nasıl kullanıldığını analiz etmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bu doğrultuda amaçlı örneklem kullanılarak Atlas dergisinin Ocak 2021-Mayıs 2021 tarih aralığında yer alan 78 reklam, nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden içerik analizi ile incelenmiştir. Analizler neticesinde yüzdelikler hesaplanıp en çok kullanılan çekicilikler ve neredeyse hiç kullanılmayan çekicilikler belirlenmiştir. Dergi reklamlarında en çok kullanılan duygusal çekicilik kalite çekiciliği olmuştur. Müşterilerin isteklerinin ve beklentilerinin karşılanması adına kalite unsurunu reklamlarında çokça uygulamışlardır. Suçluluk, kıtlık, müzik ve bireysellik duygusal reklam çekiciliklerinin nispeten çok daha az oranda yer aldığı analiz edilmiştir. Markaların dergiyi satın alan müşterilerin gözünde olumsuzluk yaşatacak durumların oluşmaması adına suçluluk ve kıtlık çekiciliklerine neredeyse hiç yer vermediği sonucu da yine bu bağlamda elde edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Reklamcılık, Dergi Reklamcılığı, Reklam Çekicilikleri, Duygusal Çekicilik.

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Introduction

Humans are emotional beings and brands that are aware of this are trying to plan their message strategies accordingly. Advertising appeals are used to design messages according to this insight. Advertising appeals, which can be defined as advertising elements based on the principle of persuasion to meet the rational and/or emotional needs and expectations of consumers in the shortest form, increase the memorability and impact of the advertisement and serve the long or short-term goals of the brands.

The basis of advertising appeals is first to draw attention to the advertising message. This process is followed by arousing curiosity about the product or service promoted by the advertising message. Ultimately, it is aimed to create an attitude change in the target audience and to transform this attitude into a behavioral change in line with the objectives of the advertisement (Khan & Khan, 2006). In line with the aforementioned objectives, brands benefit from two types of advertising appeals: rational and emotional. When deciding which appeals to include in the preparation of the advertising message, advertisers do not only consider the target audience and product/service characteristics. The brand's position in the sector and market, cultural, environmental and psychological factors are also decisive criteria in determining advertising appeals (Becan, 2014).

Emotional appeals can more easily capture the attention of target audiences, provide high memorability and ensure that less cognitive effort is spent on the advertising content. However, emotional appeals are preferred more often because they cannot be easily imitated by rival brands (Pringle & Field, 2008). The same cannot be said for rational appeals (Tellis, 2004). Rational appeals are a suitable message strategy for use in situations where the objective features of the product or service need to be highlighted. Instead of emotions, they focus on affecting the target audience's logic and rational cognitive system.

There are many classifications in the literature on advertising appeals as an important application form of creative message strategy. Although the categorization of these classifications differs from each other with some nuances, they essentially aim for one thing: to persuade the target audience. Advertising appeals are used for different purposes in different advertising messages and channels to persuade the target audience. This study aims to analyze how advertising appeals are used in magazine advertisements, also taking into account sectoral differentiation. For this purpose, first a brief conceptual overview of advertising and advertising appeals is presented, then the findings obtained through the content analysis of a total of 78

advertisements in the five-month publication period of Atlas magazine between January 2021 and May 2021 are included. Subsequently, the results obtained were evaluated considering sectoral differences and the advertising perspective, and the study was concluded.

A Brief Look at the Advertising

Although advertising can be defined most simply as “announcement”, it is not right to limit the understanding of the concept to this perspective. Advertising is defined in its most basic form as “the introduction of a product or service to a wide audience through mass communication channels by purchasing a place and time in a way that it is clear who pays for it” (Elden et al., 2015). Advertisements can serve various purposes according to the goals of the brands. The advertisement of a brand that wants to increase product sales will convey rational messages, while the advertisement of a brand that wants to position itself positively and strongly in the minds of consumers will convey emotional messages. The selection of one of these two dimensions of the advertising strategy is shaped by variables such as the brand's target audience, the type of message, and the media channel used.

Advertisements can be published through traditional mass media such as television, magazines and newspapers, as well as digital channels such as the internet and subsequently developed social media channels. Each preferred medium has its own characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages. For example, while traditional channels are not suitable for a two-way communication flow, digital channels enable interactive communication that allows feedback between the brand and the target audience. Similarly, digital media channels enable the production of personalized content; however, the structure of traditional media is not suitable for personalization (Dereli, 2023). While it seems more reasonable to prefer traditional communication channels in an advertising campaign where the target audience is determined as Generation X and Y, it will not be equally correct for a campaign that is expected to reach a young audience. The choice of media channel, which is an effective factor in the success of advertising campaigns, is important in this sense.

Advertisement has three basic functions. These can be listed as informing, persuading and reminding (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016). The informing function includes objective explanations such as specifying the technical and functional features of the advertised product or service. The persuasive function can be explained as the function in which the advertisement shapes the attitudes and perceptions of the target audience towards the brand. Finally, the reminding function can be expressed as the function in which no new

information is conveyed about the product or service or brand to be advertised, and the memorability of the brand is reinforced. As stated before, the goals of the brand also affect the form of the advertisement; therefore, it also determines the function with which the message will reach the target audience.

The success of an advertisement is shaped by answering the questions of “what will the brand say” and “how will it say it”. What the brand will say represents the message, main theme and idea to be conveyed by the advertisement. The question of how this main message will be expressed is determined by the format and text of the advertisement (Ray, 1982). These questions, which can be expressed as two components of the creative message strategy, are the basis of creating a successful advertising campaign. Carrying the right message to the right target audience at the right time, through the right channel, with a persuasive strategy is a measure that proves the success of the mentioned process. If the process works correctly, the expected behavioral change in the target audience will be created and the advertising message will have achieved its purpose (Weilbacher, 2001).

Brands use various strategies to make their advertisements stand out and reach their goals. In addition to strategies such as target audience strategy and media strategy, message strategy also strengthens or weakens the effect of an advertisement. Brands use various appeals within the scope of advertising message strategies. Although the types of advertising appeals used vary, they basically have one purpose: to persuade the target audience. The persuasion action in question is carried out with a creative message strategy, especially in cases where rational characteristics are not prominent. Using creative message strategies, the communication goal of the advertisement is concretized and thus a striking and positive effect is created on the target audience. Advertisers and advertisers basically aim to build a bond with their target audiences by appealing to them and thus ensuring that their purchasing behaviors are repeated. Accordingly, since the target audience and expectations that each advertising campaign aims to reach differ, the advertising message strategies to be used at this point also vary. What is important here is that each brand uses the most appropriate message strategy in line with its own goals and includes the right advertising appeals.

Advertising Appeals

Advertising appeals can be defined as themes used to gain the attention of target audiences and influence their thoughts and feelings about a product or service (Belch & Belch, 2021: 296). Lin (2011) explains advertising appeal in his study as “packaging a specific benefit or reason in various ways that allows the target

audience to make sense of why they buy a product or service.” The purpose of advertising appeals is to persuade the consumer to purchase the product or service. For this purpose, advertising appeals that are compatible with the objectives and target audience of the advertising campaign are integrated into advertising messages. A study conducted by Kotler and Armstrong (2006) emphasizes that advertising appeals should have three basic features. The first of these is the meaningfulness feature, which includes emphasizing the benefits and appeal of the promoted product or service. The second is that the offered product or service should provide credibility that it will meet the expectations of the consumer. Finally, it should ensure that the product or service offered is different from its competitors. The study conducted by Jovanović et al. (2016) reveals that advertising appeals have functions such as gaining potential customers, shaping awareness, belief, attitude and purchasing behavior towards the advertised product or service, as well as being a creative message strategy. Basically, two message strategies are followed in advertisements which rational and emotional. Rational message strategies emphasize the technical and price features of the product (Dix & Marchegiani, 2013: 393), while emotional message strategies aim to appeal to consumers’ emotions and establish an emotional bond with the brand. Emotional message strategies affect target audiences emotionally, either positively or negatively, with appeals such as humorous and scary elements contained in the message (Pelsmacker et al., 2002: 124). Emotional appeals are used in situations which it is difficult to rationally convey the benefits of the product or service (Panda et al., 2013). Themes such as humor, joy, guilt, nostalgia, sexuality, pride, and trust can be exemplified in the context of emotional appeals (Dix & Marchegiani, 2013). According to Stafford and Day (2013), with rational appeals, appeal is created in messages through objective transmission with real information. Themes such as performance, durability, health, and suitability can be described as rational appeals (Dix & Marchegiani, 2013). Advertisements are reflected in the form of rational appeals, logical arguments and detailed information transfer (Zhang, et al., 2014). In the context of today’s industrial society, considering that each product has more than one brand equivalent, the importance of using emotional message strategies by brands is increasing (Drewniay & Jewler, 2013: 6). Such an assessment is not valid for every sector. For example, in the service sector, using rational appeals to clarify questions in the minds of consumers may be more effective in terms of the success of the advertising message (Albers-Miller & Stafford, 1999).

The use of advertising appeals, just like any other advertising strategy, should be carried out with meticulous research and great care. For example, the

use of fear appeals is quite risky as it can lead to the exact opposite effect of what is expected, also known as the boomerang effect (Good & Abraham, 2007). In order to reduce this risk, the literature recommends using fear-based message strategies together with positive emotional advertising appeals such as humor (Gallopel-Morvan et al., 2011). Emotional advertising appeals that create a positive impact can be exemplified with many different themes such as celebrity use, irony, hope, and benefit, as well as the use of humor (Büyücek et al., 2019).

One of the most common concepts encountered in the literature on advertising related to emotions is emotional reactions such as warmth/sincerity, sadness, relief, joy, surprise, etc. shown to the advertisement. In parallel with these reactions, appeals such as fear, hedonic, humor, sexuality, and romance are used in advertisements in order to influence target audiences. In addition to the specific classification mentioned, these appeals are also grouped more generally as positive and negative appeals (Yönet, 2022). In addition, although there are many classifications of advertising appeals in the literature, it can be said that Aristotle's classification forms the basis of them. The first of Aristotle's persuasive appeals emerges with the conceptualization of ethos. Ethos refers to the physical characteristics, oratory skills, and reliability of the person in the persuasive position; in short, his charisma. The second persuasive appeal, called pathos, can be called emotional appeals. It refers to the emotional bond that will be formed between the persuader and the target audience. Finally, there is the logos persuasive appeal, which is identified with rational appeal and logic (Davidson, 1908).

There are diversion in the literature regarding the classification of advertising appeals. The first of these classifications is based on the concepts of informative appeal and emotional appeal in Davies' (1993) study titled "Developing Combinations of Message Appeals for Campaign Management". Accordingly, informative content consists of objective explanations about the product or service such as the product's price, its components, and technical usage details. Emotional appeal, on the other hand, focuses on meeting the psychosocial needs of the target audience and makes the consumption phenomenon positive or reinforces the behavior of avoiding punishment. Themes such as good citizenship, status, being a good parent and youth can be accepted within this type of appeal. Another classification was made by Moriarty (1991) who suggested that eleven types of appeals can be used in advertising. These appeals are nostalgia, fear, excitement, love, pleasure, family, pride, guilt, grief, relief and pathos. In another study conducted by Clow and Back (2009), it is seen that advertising appeals are classified under seven categories as music,

humor, emotions, reason, sexuality, scarcity and fear. In a study conducted by Hetsroni (2007), advertising appeals are categorized as adventure, beauty, collectivism, wealth, wisdom, youthful spirit, family, health, helpfulness, patriotism, kindness, savings, efficiency, security, sexuality, convenience, happiness, tradition, popularity, modernization, leisure, quality, competition, perfection and individuality. All studies and classifications in the literature show that appeal themes are essential to ensure persuasiveness in advertising. Advertising appeals that attract attention, create awareness and can be repeated at certain intervals not only affect the purchasing behavior of the target audience, but can also direct their emotions and perceptions (Chang et al., 2016; Raza et al., 2018).

Methodology

The use of magazines as an advertising tool brings with it various advantages. Prestigious readership, the ability to reach a niche audience, high print quality, flexible presentation of creativity, permanence, and readers being more willing to accept advertisements published here can be counted among these advantages (Belch & Belch, 2021: 357-358). For this reason, the aim of the study was to examine the advertising appeals used in magazine advertisements, and in this direction, the five-month publication period of Atlas magazine (January 2021-May 2021) was subjected to content analysis, one of the qualitative research methods, using purposeful sampling. Content analysis, is a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to the contexts of their use. Content analysis has its own approach to analyzing data that stems largely from how the object of analysis, content, is conceived (Krippendorff, 2004). The magazine advertisements examined in the study were analyzed by taking into account the advertising appeals determined from the literature. The preferred Atlas magazine was chosen because it is a magazine that includes all advertising categories in terms of its publication subject.

Findings

This section of the study includes the content analysis of the advertisements in the issues of Atlas magazine published in January, February, March, April and May 2021. The content analysis includes the magazine's imprint, the pages where the advertisements are located, the sectoral categorization of the advertisements and the number of appeals. This imprint can be summarized as in Table 1.

Atlas magazine is a monthly magazine published on the theme of geography. Within the scope of the study, the issues published between January 2021 and May 2021 were analyzed.

Table 1. Atlas Magazine’s Informations

Magazine Name	Publication type	Publication frequency	Numbers covered in the study
Atlas	Geography	Monthly	January 2021 February 2021 March 2021 April 2021 May 2021

As seen in Appendix 1, in the January issue of Atlas Magazine, which is considered in this study, 9 advertisements were published. When the categories of these advertisements are examined from a sectoral perspective, they are classified under the titles of tourism, bank, hotel, food, shopping, cosmetics, cargo, and shoes. Among the advertisements published, the most frequent appeal was the youth spirit appeal at a rate of 67% (n=6) and the most frequent appeal was the natural appeal at a rate of 67% (n=6). The second most frequent appeals in the advertisements are health and quality appeals at a rate of 56% (n=5). In the January issue advertisements considered in this study, the appeals of scarcity, music, curiosity, individuality, and tradition were not encountered.

As seen in Appendix 2, in the February issue of Atlas Magazine, which is examined in this study, 11 advertisements were published. When the categories of these advertisements are examined from a sectoral perspective, they are classified under the titles of airline, education, electronics, tourism, cosmetics, hotel, food, small household appliances, shopping, and shoes. Among the advertisements published, the most popular appeal was encountered at a rate of 73% (n=8). The second most common appeal among the advertisements was the quality appeal at a rate of 64% (n=7). In February, the magazine did not encounter any appeals of guilt, famine, music, or patriotism.

As shown in Appendix 3, in the March issue of Atlas Magazine, which is examined in this study, 15 advertisements were published. When the categories of these advertisements are examined from a sectoral perspective, they are classified under the titles of bank, organization, exchange, electronics, film production, hotel, food, car rental, motorcycle, application shopping, and construction industry. Among the advertisements published, the most popular, quality and success appeals were encountered at a rate of 80% (n=12). The second most common appeal among the advertisements was the perfection appeal at a rate of 60% (n=9). Fear, individuality and helpfulness appeals were not encountered at all in the March issue of the magazine.

As shown in Appendix 4, in the April issue of Atlas Magazine, which is examined in this study, 15 advertisements were published. When the categories of these advertisements are examined from a sectoral

perspective, they are classified under the titles of small home appliances, airline, bank, accessory, hotel, exchange, clothing, car rental, food, store, cargo, and shoe. The most common appeal among the advertisements is youth spirit, with a rate of 67% (n=10). The second most common appeals among the advertisements are popularity, naturalness, and quality, with a rate of 53% (n=8). Fear, shock, guilt, scarcity, music, individuality, and tradition appeals were not encountered at all in the April issue of the magazine.

Appendix 5 shows that, in the May issue of Atlas Magazine, which was examined in this study, 28 advertisements were published. In this sense, based on the dates examined in the scope of the research, the month in which the most advertisements were published was May. When the categories of these advertisements were examined from a sectoral perspective, they were classified under the titles of shoes, bank, exchange, hotel, clothing, car rental, food, shopping, holding, small household appliances, cosmetics, shoes, e-commerce, health center, cleaning, and major appliances. The most common appeal among the advertisements was naturalness appeal at a rate of 61% (n=7). The second most common appeal among the advertisements was popularity and family appeal at a rate of 54% (n=15). The third most common appeal in the issue published in May was quality appeal at a rate of 50% (n=14). Fear, shock, guilt, famine, music, and individuality appeals were not encountered at all in the magazine in May.

Conclusion and Evaluation

Advertisements are seen in magazines as in every field. Brands use advertisements to be remembered, increase their sales, impress customers, be different, be recognized, provide information and hold on. Many studies, analyzes and activities are used in order for advertisements to benefit brands. As included in this study, one of the analyzes and studies used is emotional advertising appeals. Emotional advertising appeals attract the attention of customers, affect their thoughts emotionally and continue their interaction, including at the point of purchase. It is one of the advertising analyzes that aim to establish a bond between the brand and the customer.

In this study, advertisements published in the January, February, March, April and May 2021 issues of Atlas

magazine, a geography magazine, were examined. It was determined that there were a total of 78 advertisements in the magazine issues and the analyzes were made on these advertisements. The advertisements in the magazines were examined in terms of emotional advertising appeals and a coding table was created. As a result of the analyzes, percentages were calculated and the most used appeals and the appeals that were almost never used were determined.

From this point on, the most used emotional appeal in the advertisements in the Atlas magazine issues was quality appeal with 59% (n=46). The quality of the advertiser brands was kept in the foreground. They applied the quality element in their advertisements a lot in order to meet the demands and expectations of the customers. Quality appeal was frequently included in the advertisements in order to create a sense of satisfaction, superiority and having the powerful in people. Naturalness appeal, which came in second place, was determined as 56% (n=44). Although the brands aimed to be strong, successful and on the agenda in the advertisements, they used naturalness appeal in their advertisements without overdoing it by filling it with simplicity, elegance and subtleties. The popularity appeal followed with 53% (n=41). With this appeal, people were presented with a popular status and the aim was to perceive the phenomenon in which the popular advertisements were located. Thus, in order to reach the target audience more, popularity appeal was among the most used appeals. Finally, youth spirit appeal was determined with 51% (n=40). With its youthful spirit appeal, it has targeted mostly young people. With the appeal used, it has been ensured that people read their magazines with pleasure by giving energy to the magazine and giving a youthful spirit in the advertisements. In addition, it is one of the most commonly used emotional advertising appeals in order for the brands in the advertisements to appeal to young people and increase their interest in the brands, which eventually leads to purchase.

As mentioned at the beginning, in this study, in addition to the most commonly used advertising appeals, almost unused advertising appeals have also been analyzed. Starting from this point, in the examination of 78 advertisements in Atlas magazine in a 5-month period, it has been analyzed that guilt, scarcity, music and individuality are included in the emotional advertising appeals at a rate of 1% (n=1). When compared to other appeals, these appeals have been used almost non-existent. In order to prevent situations that will create negative effects in the eyes of customers who buy the magazine, brands have almost never included guilt and scarcity appeals. In addition, regardless of the size of their target audience, in terms of existing brands producing social products

and offering services rather than individuality, music and individual appeals have been given very little space in order to avoid confusion and problems in reaching and reaching the target audience.

When the results obtained are evaluated in the context of the studies conducted in the literature, they support the judgment that various dimensions of emotional appeals are used in advertising activities. Ateş (2016) aimed to reveal the categories of appeal, types of emotional appeal and appealing tones used in political advertisements; as a result of the research, it was revealed that the rates of using rational and emotional appeal in the campaign process were quite close to each other and that there were differences between political parties in this sense. According to the same study, the most preferred type of emotional appeal is enthusiasm appeal, while the least preferred type of emotional appeal is sadness appeal. Another study by Hornik et al. (2017) aimed to quantitatively evaluate past studies on advertising persuasion types and scale them to a common scale; as a result, it was found that appeal types were not equally effective, and sexuality and humor appeals were preferred more than fear and logical appeals. Among the other results obtained from this study is the fact that emotional persuasion types are more effective on television. In the study conducted by Uğur (2021), the concepts of fear and disgust appeal, which are among the elements of negative emotional appeal, were examined, and then the Rexona "End Yellow Stains" commercial, in which both fear and disgust appeal were used together, were analyzed. Content analysis was used as the research method in the study. As a result, it was revealed that consumers were informed about the risk of using or not using a certain product through the fear and disgust appeal approaches presented to consumers in the advertisement. Emotional appeals used in advertisements can have a great impact on consumers' intention to purchase a product. Yousef et al. (2023) found that in multiple contexts, positive appeals are generally more effective than negative appeals when presented together.

In this study, which examined the advertising appeals used in magazine advertisements, it was found that brands differ in the use of appeals according to the sectors in which they operate. In this context, other academic studies can examine different types of magazines and make comparisons of the appeals used. The appeals of advertising messages in different communication channels can be analyzed. The appeals of advertising messages in different communication channels can be analyzed. Analyzing the appeals used in the content of messages based on gender discrimination in advertisements is presented as a suggestion.

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This article has been scanned by plagiarism detection softwares. No plagiarism detected.

Ethics committee approval was not sought in this study because it was not a clinical or experimental study on humans or animals that required an ethics committee decision.

Attachments

Appendix 1. Advertising Appeals in the January 2021 Issue of Atlas Magazine

Nu	Name of the Magazine	The Magazine's Category	Date of the Magazine	Page Number of the advertisement	Category of Advertising	Humor	Fear	Sexuality	Adventure	Savings	Joy	Popularity	Health	Security	Spirit of Youth	Wisdom	Wealth	Family	Shock	Guilt	Famine	Comparison	Quality	Success	Naturalness	Music	Curiosity	Beauty	Rehab	Perfection	Ease	Individuality	Benevolence	Patriotism	Modernization	Tradition	
1	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	2	Tourism	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	
2	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	5	Bank	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2
3	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	15	Hotel	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
4	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	17	Food	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
5	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	19	Shopping Center	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
6	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	21	Shopping Center	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	33	Cosmetic	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
8	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	101	Cargo	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	
9	Atlas	Geography	January,2021	102	Shoes	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
Number						There is: 1	3	1	2	2	1	3	4	5	1	6	4	2	2	0	0	0	1	5	4	6	0	0	2	1	3	1	0	2	2	2	0
						There isn't: 2	6	8	7	7	8	6	5	4	8	3	5	7	7	9	9	9	8	4	5	3	9	9	7	8	6	8	9	7	7	7	7
Percent						There is: 1	%33	%11	%22	%22	%11	%33	%44	%56	%11	%67	%44	%22	%22	%0	%0	%0	%11	%56	%44	%67	%0	%0	%22	%11	%33	%11	%0	%22	%22	%22	%0
						There isn't: 2	%67	%89	%78	%78	%89	%67	%56	%44	%89	%33	%56	%78	%78	%100	%100	%100	%89	%44	%56	%33	%100	%100	%78	%89	%67	%89	%100	%78	%78	%78	%78

Appendix 2. Advertising Appeals in the February 2021 Issue of Atlas Magazine

Nu	Name of the magazine	The magazine's category	History of the magazine	Page Number of the advertisement	Category of advertising	Humor	Fear	Sexuality	Adventure	Savings	Joy	Popularity	Health	Security	Spirit of Youth	Wisdom	Wealth	Family	Shock	Guilt	Famine	Comparison	Quality	Success	Naturalness	Music	Curiosity	Beauty	Rehab	Perfection	Ease	Individuality	Benevolence	Patriotism	Modernization	Tradition	
1	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	2	Airway	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	
2	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	7	Education	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
3	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	19	Electronics	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1
4	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	21	Tourism	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
5	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	23	Cosmetic	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	
6	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	25	Hotel	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	77	Food	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
8	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	97	Small Appliances	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	
9	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	99	Shopping Center	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
10	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	101	Shopping Center	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
11	Atlas	Geography	February,2021	102	Shoes	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
Number						There is: 1	3	2	2	2	4	3	8	3	1	5	3	2	2	1	0	0	2	7	5	5	0	1	4	2	3	3	1	2	0	2	1
						There isn't: 2	8	9	9	9	7	8	3	8	10	6	8	9	9	10	11	11	9	4	6	6	11	10	7	9	8	8	10	9	11	9	10
Percent						There is: 1	%27	%18	%18	%18	%36	%27	%73	%27	%9	%45	%27	%18	%18	%9	%0	%0	%18	%64	%45	%45	%0	%9	%36	%18	%27	%27	%9	%18	%0	%18	%9
						There isn't: 2	%73	%82	%82	%82	%64	%73	%27	%73	%91	%55	%73	%82	%82	%91	%100	%100	%82	%36	%55	%55	%100	%91	%64	%82	%73	%73	%91	%82	%100	%82	%82

Appendix 3. Advertising Appeals in the March 2021 Issue of Atlas Magazine

Nu	Name of the magazine	The magazine's category	History of the magazine	Page Number of the advertisement	Category of advertising	Humor	Fear	Sexuality	Adventure	Savings	Joy	Popularity	Health	Security	Spirit of Youth	Wisdom	Wealth	Family	Shock	Guilt	Famine	Comparison	Quality	Success	Naturalness	Music	Curiosity	Beauty	Rehab	Perfection	Ease	Individuality	Benevolence	Patriotism	Modernization	Tradition	
1	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	2	Bank	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	
2	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	7	Organization	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
3	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	9	Exchange	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
4	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	19	Electronics	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2
5	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	21	Film Production	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
6	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	23	Hotel	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	25	Food	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2
8	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	31	Car rental	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2
9	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	37	Motorcycle	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2
10	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	41	Food	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
11	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	93	Application	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2
12	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	97	Shopping Center	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
13	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	99	Shopping Center	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
14	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	101	Construction Industry	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2
15	Atlas	Geography	March,2021	102	Shoes	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Number					There is: 1	5	0	1	3	2	5	12	3	3	8	3	3	4	3	1	1	7	12	12	8	1	5	6	6	9	4	0	0	2	5	1	
					There isn't: 2	10	15	14	12	13	10	3	12	12	7	12	12	11	12	14	14	8	3	3	7	14	10	9	9	6	11	15	15	13	10	14	
Percent					There is: 1	%3	%0	%7	%20	%13	%33	%80	%20	%20	%53	%20	%20	%27	%20	%7	%7	%47	%80	%80	%53	%7	%33	%40	%40	%60	%27	%0	%0	%13	%33	%7	
					There isn't: 2	%67	%100	%93	%80	%87	%67	%20	%80	%80	%47	%80	%80	%73	%80	%93	%93	%53	%20	%20	%47	%93	%67	%60	%60	%60	%40	%73	%100	%100	%87	%67	%93

Appendix 4. Advertising Appeals in the April 2021 Issue of Atlas Magazine

Nu	Name of the magazine	The magazine's category	History of the magazine	Page Number of the advertisement	Category of advertising	Humor	Fear	Sexuality	Adventure	Savings	Joy	Popularity	Health	Security	Spirit of Youth	Wisdom	Wealth	Family	Shock	Guilt	Famine	Comparison	Quality	Success	Naturalness	Music	Curiosity	Beauty	Rehab	Perfection	Ease	Individuality	Benevolence	Patriotism	Modernization	Tradition		
1	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	2	Small Appliances	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2		
2	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	5	Airway	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	
3	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	15	Bank	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	
4	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	17	Accessories	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
5	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	19	Hotel	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
6	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	21	Exchange	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
7	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	23	Hotel	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
8	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	29	Clothing	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
9	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	31	Clothing	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
10	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	39	Car rental	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2
11	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	45	Food	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
12	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	51	Shopping Center	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
13	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	77	Shopping Center	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
14	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	95	Cargo	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	
15	Atlas	Geography	April,2021	100	Shoes	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	
Number					There is: 1	4	0	6	3	4	3	8	4	6	10	4	2	2	0	0	0	1	8	6	8	0	3	6	2	5	4	0	2	1	3	0		
					There isn't: 2	11	15	9	12	11	12	7	11	9	5	11	13	13	15	15	15	14	7	9	7	15	12	9	13	10	11	15	13	14	12	15		
Percent					There is: 1	%27	%0	%40	%20	%27	%20	%53	%27	%40	%67	%27	%13	%13	%0	%0	%0	%7	%53	%40	%53	%0	%20	%40	%13	%33	%27	%0	%13	%7	%20	%0		
					There isn't: 2	%73	%100	%60	%80	%73	%80	%47	%73	%60	%33	%73	%87	%87	%100	%100	%100	%93	%47	%60	%47	%100	%80	%60	%87	%67	%73	%100	%87	%93	%80	%100		

Appendix 5. Advertising Appeals in the May 2021 Issue of Atlas Magazine

Nu	Name of the magazine	The magazine's category	History of the magazine	Page Number of the advertisement	Category of advertising	Humor	Fear	Sexuality	Adventure	Savings	Joy	Popularity	Health	Security	Spirit of Youth	Wisdom	Wealth	Family	Shock	Guilt	Famine	Comparison	Quality	Success	Naturalness	Music	Curiosity	Beauty	Rekabet	Perfection	Ease	Individuality	Benevolence	Patriotism	Modernization	Tradition
1	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	2	Shoes	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	5	Bank	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2
3	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	15	Hotel	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
4	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	17	Exchange	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
5	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	19	Hotel	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
6	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	21	Clothing	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	25	Car rental	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2
8	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	29	Food	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
9	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	47	Shopping center	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
10	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	101	Shopping center	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
11	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	102	Holding	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1
12	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	104	Small appliances	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
13	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	107	Cosmetics	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
14	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	109	Small appliances	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1
15	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	111	Small appliances	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2
16	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	113	Small appliances	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2
17	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	114	Shoes	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
18	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	119	Small appliances	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
19	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	121	Shoes	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
20	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	123	E-commerce	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
21	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	127	Small appliances	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2
22	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	129	Health center	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
23	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	131	Cleaning	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2
24	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	133	Cosmetics	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2
25	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	135	Major appliances	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2
26	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	143	Cleaning	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2
27	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	145	Food	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2
28	Atlas	Geography	May,2021	146	Small appliances	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2
Number					There is: 1	3	0	7	2	10	11	9	7	11	11	8	1	15	0	0	0	3	14	11	17	0	2	11	3	10	4	0	3	5	4	2
Number					There isn't: 2	25	28	21	26	18	17	19	21	17	17	20	27	13	28	28	28	25	14	17	11	28	26	17	25	18	24	28	25	23	24	26
Percent					There is: 1	%11	%0	%25	%7	%36	%39	%32	%25	%39	%39	%29	%4	%54	%0	%0	%0	%11	%50	%39	%61	%0	%7	%39	%11	%36	%14	%0	%11	%18	%14	%7
Percent					There isn't: 2	%89	%100	%75	%93	%64	%61	%68	%75	%61	%61	%71	%96	%46	%100	%100	%100	%89	%50	%61	%39	%100	%93	%61	%89	%64	%86	%100	%89	%82	%86	%93